

Research for Impact in Digital Innovation

Proceedings of the 3rd RIDI Workshop
in conjunction with 38th Bled eConference

Bled (SI), June 8, 2025

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Preface

Topics like Digital Transformation and Business Model Innovation are currently driving initiatives in industry; not only to introduce new technologies but also to gain significant business benefits. Hence, technology is not just seen as a means on its own but as one factor among others. Each digitally innovative project needs to incorporate the context of an organisation (market, customer segments) as well as its organisation and staff members. Challenges during such an endeavour are manifold. As a result, there is also an increased need in practice for more explicit guidance in terms of lessons learned, methods, approaches, principles, and design concepts. Developing, and operationalizing, such explicit guidance entails demand-driven research and education, requiring synergies between applied research and practice. It also sparks a need for effective research methods that balance real world needs and contexts with scientific rigour.

Hence, a platform for individuals contributing to the development of explicit guidance for digital innovation by using research methods is required. Such a platform should bring together practitioners and academics, including researchers within the context of technical and applied sciences. The platform fosters exchange by discussing success stories and experiences from the field together with methodological approaches. It, furthermore, represents a trigger for shaping a research agenda together with corresponding methods in order to enable research in practice.

In line with this, the third European workshop on Research for Impact in Digital Innovation (RIDI 2025) aimed to bring together practitioners and researchers who are working in the area of digital innovation. It was conducted in conjunction with the 38th Bled eConference on June 8, 2025. The workshop started with an introduction to an ongoing discussion on the future of science in order to motivate a similar discourse during the RIDI workshop. This was further supported by four presentations elaborating on different aspects of research for impact. For the first time, RIDI hosted a one-hour mini-workshop on digitalisation and sustainability. The proceedings at hand bundles abstracts to the presentations as well as a short description of the mini-workshop.

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EXPLORING ORGANIZATIONAL READINESS FOR DIGITAL4SUSTAINABILITY: A PRACTICAL WORKSHOP ON SKILLS AND CAPABILITY DEVELOPMENT

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As the twin transformation—combining digitalization and sustainability—accelerates, organizations face increasing pressure to adapt. Drawing on insights from the European Digital4Sustainability initiative, we integrate theory and practice to emphasize the importance of building a digitally competent and sustainability-oriented workforce as a foundation for organizational resilience. This interactive workshop leverages Twin Transformation pathways (Aagaard & Vanhaverbeeke, 2024) to explore the skills and competencies professionals and organizations need to navigate this shift effectively. After a brief introduction to core concepts and frameworks, participants will engage in a hands-on exercise to assess and reflect on their own and their organization’s twin transformation readiness.

Keywords:

Twin transformation, skills, capabilities, sustainability, digitalization

Research Impact

This workshop translates theoretical insights from the Digital4Sustainability research project—particularly the needs analysis (Jonkers & Vester, 2024), into practical reflection exercises for professionals and organizations. The analysis highlights significant current and expected gaps in digital and sustainability-related skills, which are critical for aligning with a future-proof labor market. While low-skilled labor is increasingly automated, new roles demand more complex, diverse, and higher-educated skill profiles—requirements unlikely to be met by a single employee. This shift is already creating a noticeable skill mismatch across sectors.

Educational systems are struggling to keep pace with the speed of the twin transition, and relevant applied research remains limited. This workshop seeks to foster research impact by bridging the gap between academic insight (Christmann et al., 2024; Kürpick et al., 2023) and real-world application. By encouraging participants to reflect on their individual and organizational learning needs, the session supports the development of actionable strategies for workforce transformation in line with the demands of the digital and green economy.

Duration: 60 minutes (10-minute informative presentation & 50-minute interactive session)

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EXPLORING REFLECTIVE DATA-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING THROUGH SIMULATION PEDAGOGY AND DIGITAL ENVIRONMENTS

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Keywords:

digital learning,
data-driven
decisions,
simulation
pedagogy,
smart farming

1 Introduction

As work environments and knowledge landscapes become more complex, the ability to make reflective, data-driven decisions is increasingly essential. Decision-making has emerged as a crucial skill for employers across various sectors. For example, in agriculture, which is undergoing some of its most significant changes in decades due to both digitalisation and climate change (Griffin et al., 2018) the complexity of decision-making is rising, such as in determining precision fertilisation strategies or optimal harvest timing (Nowak, 2021). As sectors such as agriculture, healthcare, and engineering increasingly rely on data-driven decisions, educational innovations are urgently required to support students' cognitive processes and metacognitive awareness during learning.

Smart farming, which employs the latest technological innovations to optimize crop production, highlights the need for more advanced decision-making frameworks. Simulation pedagogy offers a powerful framework for fostering professional skills development, enabling learners to engage in realistic decision-making tasks in a controlled yet dynamic environment that mirror real-world challenges — for

example, through the use of digital twins (Peladarinos et al., 2023; Verdouw, 2021; Lateef, 2010). In environments like smart farming, where uncertainty and data overload are prevalent, integrating simulation pedagogy can assist learners in navigating complex decisions and improve their ability to reflect on the consequences of their choices.

2 Research and development aims

This research and development project aims to create effective pedagogical solutions that strengthen decision-making and metacognitive skills, ultimately contributing to sustainable practices and enhancing data literacy in an increasingly complex digital environment. It explores the integration of simulation pedagogy in digital learning environments. This research and development initiative positions itself at the intersection of digital learning innovation, simulation pedagogy and cognitive science, aiming to enhance reflective decision-making through applied, practice-based development work. Co-creation, guided by design thinking (Brown, 2009), is steering the collaborative development process, engaging farmers, agricultural advisors, educators, students, and industry partners to ensure user-centered and sustainable solutions. We develop pedagogical solutions based on simulation pedagogy, integrating diverse dynamic data sources from a farm's digital twin to support experiential learning and strengthen the decision-making skills of farmers and students.

3 Methodology and practices

This research aims to explore the effectiveness of digital twin enabled simulations and a reflective learning process in supporting data-driven decision-making. The research questions focus on e.g. how digital learning environments can foster experiential learning by simulating real-world scenarios. Additionally we aim to explore the role of multiprofessional co-creation in shaping effective learning environments, and how these tools can be adapted to meet the needs of different stakeholders in the agricultural sector.

In the initial phase, we focused on identifying data requirements for the environment and integrating them into the farm's digital twin. At the same time, we developed a learner-centered pedagogical process based on learning design principles, where the

digital learning platform serves as an environment for both individual and collaborative practice of iterative, data-driven decision making.

After the initial phase, we have moved to the B-testing phase, where we are now testing our solution with a limited target group. This phase involves farmers and students, providing them with hands-on experience with the system, and simultaneously gathering feedback on digital twin usability, decision-making support, and reflective learning processes. The results of this testing phase will guide further refinement of the solution and its pedagogical approach.

The next phases involve expanding the testing to include broader target groups and online and blended learning, where we focus on multiprofessional and multilingual groups of students and farmers. Through these tests we aim to ensure that the learning environments accommodates diverse backgrounds and fosters inclusive learner-centered approach. We apply methods for collecting real-time data on students' reflection and decision-making processes. Special attention is given to approaches inspired by the think-aloud principle from cognitive science, adapted for the context, which focus is on lightweight data collection techniques that support the natural flow of student reflections which are triggered after key decision points. This approach fosters the development of students' metacognitive skills and strengthens data-driven decision-making competence, particularly in application areas like agriculture, where decisions are often made in uncertain and rapidly changing information environments.

4 Initial conclusions

The expected impact of this work is significant for the agricultural community, as it addresses the urgent need to strengthen farmers' and students' abilities to lead farming practices with data-driven decision-making. This research supports the advancement of sustainable smart farming practices by developing new pedagogical solutions across diverse educational contexts. This research and development work contributes to understanding how the combination of simulation pedagogy and digital twin solutions can be scaled and adapted to support sustainable, data-driven decision-making across different sectors in the future.

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COM-B MODEL AND THE BEHAVIOUR CHANGE WHEEL (BCW)

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Why is scientific knowledge often not effective in practice? Why don't new innovations always work well? Why do we often see limited behaviour change? To understand this, the COM-B model is a highly useful tool.

Keywords:

behaviour change,
intervention,
psychological
capability,
physical capability

1 What is the COM-B model?

The COM-B model brings together various behavioural science theories and models into a single framework. It helps explain what is needed for behaviour to occur or change. The model consists of three core components, and to change behaviour, at least one of these components must be addressed. Before applying theory to practice, it is essential to carefully consider these elements:

- **Capability** – Does the individual have the necessary knowledge and skills to understand, use, or apply it?
 - Physical capability: physical skills or abilities
 - Psychological capability: knowledge, cognitive ability
- **Opportunity** – Is it easy to understand or use? Is it accessible to everyone? Is it socially accepted or desirable?
 - Physical opportunity: time, resources, environment
 - Social opportunity: social support, social norms
- **Motivation** – Why would someone use it? Is it attractive, urgent, enjoyable? Does it align with the person's values?
 - Reflective motivation: conscious decision-making, beliefs
 - Automatic motivation: habits, impulses, emotions

2 The Behaviour Change Wheel (BCW)

The Behaviour Change Wheel is built around the COM-B model. It helps to identify and design effective behaviour change interventions.

Figure 1: The behaviour change wheel

Key step: Define the target behaviour you want to promote and use the COM-B model to analyse why it is not yet occurring. Then, brainstorm potential interventions based on that analysis.

Interventions must meet the APEASE criteria:

- **Acceptability** – To what extent is the intervention (or its components) likely to be seen as acceptable and engaging by the target group?
- **Practicability** – Can the intervention be delivered as intended and at the intended scale?
- **Effectiveness** – Is the intervention likely to achieve the desired outcome and provide value for money?
- **Affordability** – Can it be implemented within the available budget?
- **Spillover effects** – Are there any unintended positive or negative consequences?
- **Equity** – Will the intervention reduce or increase inequalities?

When selecting an intervention, work closely with key stakeholders. Use the APEASE criteria collaboratively to determine the most suitable intervention. During the session we will not only discuss the theory but will also show how this is used in practice. Furthermore, we invite participants to discuss possible applications in their domains of research.

GRADUATES' FUTURE SKILLS FOR IMPACT IN ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE

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Concepts, methods and tools in Enterprise Architecture are very abstract for students who are not familiar with business organisations and their social dynamics. So far teaching EA can only cover methods and tools, but will not show the impact of a good (or bad) EA. The submission at hand advocates to involve students into practical projects in cooperation with industry partners so that students experience the impact of their work, hence, integrating learning with research for impact. Semi-structured interviews have been conducted in order to reveal required skills and competencies from an employer's perspective. Preliminary results show that higher education needs to support students with managing their own learning and getting motivated for solving real-life problems.

Keywords:

education,
future skills,
applied research,
impact,
project-based
learning

1 Introduction

There is a current shift at Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) from classical teaching towards activity-based learning methods where students play an active role in their learning journey. Various activities and studies support this trend as industry has a lower demand for (technology or method) specialist but employees who aim to solve issues independently or create new ideas. One example for a set of skills required in the future is represented by 4C (Kivunja 2015):

- *Creator*: create results independently and evaluate/ensure quality
- *Collaborator*: collaboration within a team and with other teams
- *Communicator*: understand and explain concepts to various stakeholders
- *Critical Thinker*: solve problems in a structured way and analyze root causes

This results in a demand for adequate learning methods (*learning* in contrast to *teaching*) like for example project-based or problem-based learning (Sarangi and Ramachandran 2024) as well as inquiry-based learning (Chitman-Booker and Kopp 2013). At the same time, UAS are also shaping their profile for applied research by performing post-graduate study programs and projects together with industry-partners. This provides a chance for students to build skills for their professional future with companies in a university environment as project-based learning is supposed to foster the 4C. However, it is necessary to evaluate future skills with industry partners. The submission at hands summarizes results from interviews with practitioners aiming to identify expected skills (of graduates) that are required for working in Enterprise Architecture (EA).

2 Interview Structure

Semi-structured interviews were started in January 2025 and will continue until fall 2025. So far, 11 people participated, located in different regions in Germany and in different roles (Management, CIO, EA, Consultant). They were asked the following questions:

- Q1: Which skills and competencies are required for a good EA in your company?
- Q2: Which skills and competencies do you expect from a graduate of a master's program in Business Information Systems if they are supposed to work in EA?
- Q3: Which deficiencies do you perceive with current graduates working in your company?
- Q4: Which skills and competencies related to EA would you expect to be taught in higher education?

Answers are noted during interviews and evaluated by using a qualitative analysis. Keywords are derived from the answers and then categorized.

3 Preliminary Results and Discussion

An excerpt from the interview results is summarized in Table 1 by associating each question with the corresponding top three categories. The *perspectives* category encompasses the ability to cover different viewpoints and levels of abstraction as

well as being a generalist (rather than a specialist). *Commitment* addresses motivational aspects like (pro-active) problem solving and the individual’s willingness to learn and develop own competencies. Communication skills were mentioned in various flavors (listening, expression, language skills). *Professional competence*, such as technical skills, EA methods and domain knowledge, are not in the top three expected competencies for EA (Q1) but expected from master students (Q2). Question three aims to identify expected skills that are still missing from current graduates. Many interviewees mention *experience* but are well aware of the fact that people just finishing university will not have much business experience. It is rather meant as an idea to integrate project work and case studies in order to get experience already at the UAS (cf. Q4). Furthermore, companies would expect more methodological expertise, i.e. the ability to chose a proper method or tool based on a given problem or situation.

Table 1: Preliminary results

	Categories (top 3)	Skills (examples)
Q1	Perspectives, commitment, communication	Abstraction, generalist, problem-solving, willingness to learn, communication
Q2	Commitment, professional competence, perspectives	Willingnes to learn, technical and domain knowledge, abstraction, generalist
Q3	Commitment, experience, perspectives	Willingness to learn, problem-solving, business, project work, abstraction
Q4	Methods, experience, commitment	Modelling, methodological expertise, case study, projects, self reflection

source: own research

The intermediate results so far show that there is a need for technical and EA method skills, but there is also an emphasis on motivation and a person’s ability to manage his or her own learning process during the professional career. Interviewees also advocate more practice during learning so that students develop organizational and communication skills. In line with the 4C, students should become problem solver and critical thinker to make an impact. Consequently, project-based learning will be incorporated with research projects provided by industry partners so that students have an early exposure to current demands and learn how to solve practical problems.

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USING LLMs IN ANALYZING CODE OF CONDUCTS FOR BRIDGING THE GAP IN A LEGAL VACUUM

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Keywords:

Core Values
Data
Ethics
Legal Vacuum
LLM
Moral Compass

This study explores the intricate decision-making dynamics in a ‘legal gap’—a scenario where no explicit rules, laws, or regulations govern feasible technology research, design, or implementation. Numerous laws exist, such as those prohibiting harm or loss of life during healthcare medication development and provisional regulations addressing liability for autonomous vehicles in experimental stages. When ChatGPT launched in November 2022, laws governing intellectual property rights and privacy were in place, but transparency was not adequately regulated. The AI Act had a delay to govern technologies such as generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) including ChatGPT. However, laws, rules, and regulations often fail to fully address specific situations, creating a legal gap or vacuum. Moor uses the term ‘policy vacuum’ to describe situations where new technologies introduce activities that existing ethical policies cannot adequately address, resulting in a lack of clear guidelines for managing their implications. We consider the legal vacuum as a subset of a policy vacuum. This inquiry into the legal gap is particularly pertinent given the rapid pace of technological advancements, which often outstrip the development of corresponding regulatory frameworks. By examining core values across different business sectors, the research aims to uncover the underlying principles guiding organizational behavior in the absence of legal constraints. Furthermore, the study seeks to balance objectivity with personal values in creating a code of conduct, utilizing Large Language Model (LLM)s to assist in the analysis. The study builds on frameworks such as Value Sensitive Design (VSD) and Guidance Ethics that state that values are prominent. However, it is left to the users to establish defined values, which is a challenging decision-making process.

To this end, several critical research questions are posed: How do organizations navigate decision-making without explicit legal mandates or prohibitions? How do

core values vary across different business sectors, and what metrics can effectively measure the validity of LLMs in extracting these values? Moreover, the research delves into maintaining objectivity while acknowledging the inherent subjectivity in all knowledge and discourse.

In the data collection phase, publicly available information from commercial and non-profit organizations is scrutinized. A comprehensive dataset of core values is curated using sources such as the Fortune 500 list and various compilations of Non Profit Organization (NPO)s. The methodology involves manual identification and LLM-assisted extraction of core values, ensuring a broad and representative sample of organizational cultures.

Subsequently, the study evaluates the validity of these core values using a set of defined metrics. These include accuracy, bias, completeness, consistency, and relevance —each providing a different lens to assess the extracted values’ reliability and objectivity. The process also involves reducing the initial list of values to a more manageable and coherent set, ensuring that the essence of each original term is preserved while avoiding redundancy.

By incorporating multiple LLMs and human judgment, the study aims to mitigate bias and enhance the validity of the extracted core values. This rigorous approach allows for a nuanced understanding of how organizations articulate their core values in a legal vacuum, providing valuable insights for academic inquiry and practical application. We make a clear distinction between core values, ethical framework, code of conduct, and the decision-making process. In this paper, core values are beliefs and convictions stated in codes of conduct that shape behavior, based on and related to culture, tradition, and religion. These values arise from and shape culture, influencing areas such as gender identity, religion like the Ten Commandments, tradition such as national days, and education like critical thinking. An ethical framework, model, method, or toolbox is a structured approach that facilitates the assessment of context, stakeholders, and key issues by applying values, standards, and moral principles to ethical reasoning. In this paper, ‘context’ refers to anything that influences a decision but is not part of mission, vision, strategy, or operational objectives. ‘Stakeholders’ refer to anyone or anything that affects a decision or is affected by a decision. A code of conduct is a set of core values materialized in a set of rules how to behave in on organization. The decision-making process concerns the assumptions, processes, and stakes that influence an outcome.

This research addresses a critical gap in understanding how organizations navigate the complex interplay of technology, ethics, and regulation. It offers a systematic

framework for analyzing core values, contributing to the broader discourse on governance and ethical decision-making in the modern technological landscape. The contribution of practitioners lies in providing a structured decision-making process for collecting, validating, evaluating, and assessing values to establish a code of conduct. Additionally, the discussion on the use and caution of LLMs enhances practitioners' ability to explore and work efficiently. For researchers, the contribution is an in-depth exploration of ethical methods related to core values. The usage of LLMs has already been deployed by others. The contribution for education is the exploration and experience of knowledge, skills, and attitude.

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Program

Sunday, June 8

- 10:00 Welcome by the organisers and introduction
Cultural change in science at universities
Erik Proper et al.
- 11:00 First experiences with a professional doctorate
Guido Ongena
- 11:30 break
- 11:45 Digital4Sustainability: A Practical Workshop on Skills and Capability Development
Tara Vester, Anand Sheombar
- 12:45 lunch
- 13:30 Exploring Reflective Data-Driven Decision-Making through Simulation Pedagogy and Digital Environments
Satu Aksovaara, Hannu Haapala and Minna Silvennoinen
- Behaviour Change Presentation: COM-B Model and the Behaviour Change Wheel
Mats Belgers
- 14:30 break
- 14:45 Graduates' Future Skills for Impact in Enterprise Architecture
Jürgen Jung
- Using LLMs in Analyzing Code of Conducts for Bridging the Gap in a Legal Vacuum
Theo Theunissen
- 15:45 Wrap-up and summary
- 17:30 Conference reception